

Studies on Outer-sphere Association of some Cobalt(III) Mixed Ligand Complexes in Aqueous Solutions

NONGMALIHM RAJMUHON SINGH, NONGMALIHM RAJIN SINGH and AKOIAM MANIHAR SINGH*

Department of Chemistry, Manipur University, Imphal-795 003

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The outer-sphere association of Co^{III} mixed ligand complexes of the type [Co(L)(AMUH)₂]X₃ (L = ethylenediamine, 2,2'-dipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline; AMUH = 1-amidino-O-alkylurea; X = Cl, Br and I) has been studied. Conductometric studies of the equilibrium [Co(L)(AMUH)₂]³⁺ + X⁻ ⇌ {[Co(L)(AMUH)₂]X²⁺} have been carried out in aqueous solution at 25 ± 0.1°. The association constants of the outer-sphere complexes follow the order: (a) Cl⁻ > Br⁻ > I⁻ and (b) ethylenediamine > 2,2'-dipyridine > 1,10-phenanthroline. Sizes of the ion-pairs have also been evaluated from limiting conductance data using Bjerrum equation.

Outer-sphere complexes have been studied for some homoligand cobalt(III) complexes using conductometry¹⁻⁶ and spectrophotometry⁷⁻¹¹. More recently, Minorov and co-workers studied spectrophotometrically the outer-sphere association of ethylenediamine bis(1,10-phenanthroline)cobalt(III)¹⁵ and diacidobis(1,2-diaminoethane)cobalt(III)¹⁶ with halides, NCS and ClO₄⁻ ions in aqueous solution. The present study deals with the conductance behaviour and the ion-pair formation of ethylenediamine bis(1-amidino-O-alkylurea)-cobalt(III), (2,2'-dipyridyl)bis(1-amidino-O-methylurea)-cobalt(III) and (1,10-phenanthroline)bis(1-amidino-O-methylurea)cobalt(III) halides in aqueous solution at 25 ± 0.1°. The sizes of the ion-pairs have been evaluated from limiting conductance data using Stoke's law and from the association constants using Bjerrum relationship.

Results and Discussion

An approximate value of equivalent conductivity at infinite dilution Λ_{appr}^0 , is obtained by plotting Λ_{exp} vs $\sqrt{C}$. The Λ_{appr}^0 is fitted into Onsager's conductivity equation and the theoretical slope b is obtained.

$$\Lambda_{\text{exp}} = \Lambda_{\text{appr}}^0 - \frac{[0.7852 |Z_1|Z_2| \frac{q\Lambda_{\text{appr}}^0}{1 + \sqrt{q}} + 30.32(|Z_1| + |Z_2|)] \sqrt{2c}}{\sqrt{2c}} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{i.e., } \Lambda_{\text{exp}} = \Lambda_{\text{appr}}^0 - b\sqrt{C} \quad (2)$$

In deriving the values of b , the ionic conductivities of chloride, bromide and iodide were taken as 76.34, 78.4

and 76.8 respectively¹⁶. From the plots of $\Lambda_{\text{exp}} + b\sqrt{C}$ against C (Fig. 1), an accurate value of equivalent conductivity at infinite dilution, $\Lambda_{\text{onsager}}^0$ is obtained. The calculated value of Λ_{appr}^0 , $\Lambda_{\text{onsager}}^0$ and mean Λ_i^0 for the complexes are given in Table 1. The deviation of the Λ_{exp} vs $\sqrt{C}$ plot from the theoretical Onsager line, i.e. a plot of $\Lambda (= \Lambda_{\text{onsager}}^0 - b\sqrt{C})$ vs $\sqrt{C}$ (Figs. 2 and 3) is considered to be due to the outer-sphere association of the complex cation and anion,

TABLE 1-CONDUCTANCE DATA OF [Co(L)(AMUH)₂]X₃

Sl no	Compd *	Λ_{appr}^0	$\Lambda_{\text{onsager}}^0$	Λ_i^0 (cation)	Λ_i^0 Mean
1	[Co(en)(AMUH) ₂]Cl ₃	137.68	135.05	59.71	60.39
	[Co(en)(AMUH) ₂]Br ₃	140.44	139.09	60.99	
	[Co(en)(AMUH) ₂]I ₃	138.31	137.27	60.47	
2	[Co(2,2'-dipy)(AMUH) ₂]Cl ₃	135.85	134.33	57.99	59.37
	[Co(2,2'-dipy)(AMUH) ₂]I ₃	138.48	137.54	60.74	
3	[Co(1,10-phen)(AMUH) ₂]Cl ₃	134.85	133.88	57.54	58.50
	[Co(1,10-phen)(AMUH) ₂]I ₃	134.84	136.25	59.45	

* L=en or 2,2'-dipy or 1,10-phen, en=ethylenediamine, 2,2'-dipy = 2,2'-dipyridyl, 1,10 phen = 1,10-phenanthroline, AMUH = 1-amidino-O-methylurea, X = Cl or Br or I

The dissociation constant corresponding to the above equilibrium,

$$K = \frac{[\text{X}^-][\text{Co(L)(AMUH)}_2]^{3+}}{[\text{Co(L)(AMUH)}_2]\text{X}\}^{2+}} \quad (4)$$

has been calculated as follows. The experimental solution is taken as a mixture of (i) 3 : 1 valent salt of molar

Fig. 1. Onsager extrapolation : (a) [Co(en)(AMUH)₂]Cl₃, (b) [Co(en)(AMUH)₂]Br₃, (c) [Co(en)(AMUH)₂]I₃, (d) [Co(o-phen)(AMUH)₂]Cl₃, (e) [Co(o-phen)(AMUH)₂]I₃, (f) [Co(α,α'-dipy)(AMUH)₂]Cl₃, and (g) [Co(α,α'-dipy)(AMUH)₂]I₃.

concentration m , (ii) 2 : 1 valent salt of molar concentration $(1-\alpha)m$, where m is the molar concentration of the salt and α the degree of dissociation of the ion pair. The Onsager equation for 3 : 1 valent salt can be written as

$$\Lambda_{3:1} = \Lambda_{\text{onsager}}^0 - b' \sqrt{I} \quad (5)$$

where b' is the slope calculated in the case of b using $\Lambda_{\text{onsager}}^0$ in place of Λ_{appr}^0 while fitting into Onsager's conductivity equation¹⁸, and I is the ionic strength,

$$I = (1+\alpha)C \quad (6)$$

where C is the concentration in equivalents per litre. The Onsager equation for 2 : 1 valent salt $\{[\text{Co}(\text{L})(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{X}\}\text{X}_2$ is represented as

$$\Lambda_{2:1} = \Lambda_{\text{ion-pair}}^0 - b'' \sqrt{I} \quad (7)$$

where b'' is the slope calculated as b and b' using $\Lambda_{\text{ion-pair}}^0$ instead of Λ_{appr}^0 and $\Lambda_{\text{onsager}}^0$ respectively. $\Lambda_{\text{ion-pair}}^0$ for 2 : 1 ion-pair is derived from the relation²,

$$\frac{\Lambda_{\text{ion-pair}}^0}{[\text{Co}(\text{L})(\text{AMUH})_2]^{3+}} = \frac{|Z|}{3} \quad (8)$$

where $|Z|$ is the charge of the ion-pair, i.e. +2. The solvent corrected specific conductivity of the solution is given by

$$10^3 K = 3\alpha m \Lambda_{3:1} + 2(1-\alpha)m \Lambda_{2:1}$$

and the equivalent conductivity is given by

$$\Lambda_{\text{exp}} = \alpha \Lambda_{3:1} + \frac{2}{3} (1-\alpha) \Lambda_{2:1} \quad (9)$$

At first α is assumed to be unity and the corresponding value of I obtained from equation (6) is used in equation (9), thereby giving a truer value to α (with which

Fig. 2. Conductivities of (a) [Co(en)(AMUH)₂]Cl₃, (b) [Co(en)(AMUH)₂]Br₃, and (c) [Co(en)(AMUH)₂]I₃; upper line shows calculated Λ ($\Lambda_{\text{onsager}}^0 - bC^{1/2}$) vs $C^{1/2}$; lower line shows Λ_{exp} vs $C^{1/2}$.

a truer value of I is obtained) which is again fed into equation (6) and in this way the cycle is repeated till the constant value of α is obtained. Equation (4) can be written as

$$K = \frac{(2 + \alpha)\alpha m f_1 f_3}{(1-\alpha)f_2} \quad (10)$$

where the activity coefficients f_1 , f_2 and f_3 of X^- , $\{[\text{Co}(\text{L})(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{X}\}^{2+}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{L})(\text{AMUH})_2]^{3+}$ have been calculated from the Debye-Hückel equation¹⁹,

$$\log f_i = -0.509 Z_i^2 \sqrt{I} \quad (11)$$

where f_i refers to activity coefficients of the Z_i ions. The computed values of K_Λ for ethylenediamine bis(1-amidino-*O*-methylurea)cobalt(III) chloride, bromide and iodide; (1,10-phenanthroline)bis(1-amidino-*O*-methylurea)cobalt(III) chloride and iodide; (2,2'-dipyridyl)bis(1-amidino-*O*-methylurea)cobalt(III) chloride and iodide are given in Table 2. Comparison of these values with those of $\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{X}\}^{2+}$ (Refs.

2,5,8,13), $\{[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]\text{X}\}^{2+}$ (Refs. 2,8,13), $\{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]\text{X}\}^{2+}$ (Ref. 6), $\{[\text{Co}(\text{APT})_2]\text{Cl}\}$ (Ref. 20) and $\{[\text{Cr}(\text{GBH})_3]\text{X}\}^{2+}$ (Ref. 21), where en = ethylenediamine, BigH = biguanide, APT = acetylpyridinethiosemicarbazole, GBH = 2-guadinium benzimidazole; X = Cl, Br, I, 0.5 SO_4 , shows that the association constants increase in the order : $\text{I}^- < \text{Br}^- < \text{Cl}^- < \text{SO}_4^{2-}$.

Evans and Gardam²², and Pethybridge and Spiers²³ showed that with a common cation, the solvation of halides increase in the order : $\text{I}^- < \text{Br}^- < \text{Cl}^-$. The ion-pair formation prefers the more solvated form, i.e. $\text{I}^- < \text{Br}^- < \text{Cl}^-$. Further, it seems very likely that hydrogen bonds play a very important role in the formation of outer-sphere complexes²⁴. Ligand (anions) of the outer-sphere may be bound by hydrogen bonds to the ligands (ammine group of the 1-amidino-*O*-alkyl group) of the inner-sphere. Since the electronegativity is in the order : $\text{Cl} > \text{Br} > \text{I}$, the strength of hydrogen bond will be in the same order and hence the association constant will also be decreased in the same consequence. With the sulphates, the association constants of ion-pairs have fairly large values. In addition to large charge hydrogen bonds between the ammine groups and the oxyanion contribute to the stability of

the complex. Also with a common outer anion, the association constant decreases with increasing size of the coordination sphere : $\{[\text{Co}(\text{en}) (\text{AMUH})_2]\text{X}\}^{2+} > \{[\text{Co}(2,2'\text{-dipy}) (\text{AMUH})_2]\text{X}\}^{2+} > \{[\text{Co}(1,10\text{-phen}) (\text{AMUH})_2]\text{X}\}^{2+}$ (en = ethylenediamine; 2,2'-dipy = 2,2'-dipyridyl; 1,10-phen = 1,10-phenanthroline; X = Cl, I).

During the calculation of association constant, the dissociation of the complex ion itself is neglected. Chromium and cobalt are transition elements with a marked tendency to form coordination links. Hunt and Taube²⁵ showed in a series of ingenious experiments using O^{18} as tracer that the ion $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ exchanges its water with the solvent quite slowly, the half-life being about 40 h, while the single water molecule of the $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5.\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ ion has a half-life of 24.5 h²⁶. Since our conductance measurements have been conducted within a few hours, such exchange of inner-ligands with solvent molecules or dissociation of complex ion itself can be neglected to a good approximation.

TABLE 2—COMPUTED VALUE OF OUTER-SPHERE ASSOCIATION, K_A FOR $\{[\text{Co}(\text{L})(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{X}\}_2$ AT $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$

Ion-pair	K_A
$\{[\text{Co}(2,2'\text{-dipy}) (\text{AMUH})_2] \text{Cl}\}^{2+}$	39.74
$\{[\text{Co}(2,2'\text{-dipy}) (\text{AMUH})_2] \text{I}\}^{2+}$	23.91
$\{[\text{Co}(1,10\text{-phen}) (\text{AMUH})_2] \text{Cl}\}^{2+}$	25.93
$\{[\text{Co}(1,10\text{-phen}) (\text{AMUH})_2] \text{I}\}^{2+}$	14.64
$\{[\text{Co}(\text{en}) (\text{AMUH})_2] \text{Cl}\}^{2+}$	42.29
$\{[\text{Co}(\text{en}) (\text{AMUH})_2] \text{Br}\}^{2+}$	32.15
$\{[\text{Co}(\text{en}) (\text{AMUH})_2] \text{I}\}^{2+}$	25.11

Sizes of ion-pairs : Bjerrum²⁷ based on electrostatic interaction, gives the relation between association constant (K_A) of the ion-pairs and size of the ion as

$$K_A = \frac{4\pi N}{1000} \left(\frac{|Z_1 Z_2| e^2}{DkT} \right) Q(b) \quad (12)$$

$$Q(b) = \int_a^b x^{-1} e^x dx$$

$$x = \frac{|Z_1 Z_2| e^2}{DrkT}$$

$b = |Z_1 Z_2| e^2 / aDKT$, a represents the closest approach of the ions forming the ion-pair. From the experimental association constant we calculated the values of $Q(b)$, and from the $Q(b)$ value, the value of b was obtained

Fig. 3. Conductivities of (a) $[\text{Co}(\alpha,\alpha'\text{-dipy})(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{Cl}$, (b) $[\text{Co}(\alpha,\alpha'\text{-dipy})(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{I}$, (c) $[\text{Co}(o\text{-phen})(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{Cl}$, and (d) $[\text{Co}(o\text{-phen})(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{I}$; upper line shows calculated $\Lambda (= \Lambda_{\text{theor}}^0 - bC^{1/2})$ vs $C^{1/2}$; lower line shows Λ_{exp} vs $C^{1/2}$.

from the standard table²⁸ and hence a can be calculated.

A quantitative relation between ion mobilities and their ionic radii is expressed by Stoke's law²³, which in terms of conductivity in aqueous solution at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ becomes

$$a = \frac{9.16 \times 10^{-7} Z_i}{\Lambda_i} \quad (13)$$

TABLE 3—APPROXIMATE RADII OF $\{[Co(L)(AMUH)_2]\}^{3+}$ AND ION-PAIRS $\{[Co(L)(AMUH)_2]X\}^{2+}$

Cation/Anion/Ion-pair	Radius from Stoke's law a (Å)	Radius from eqn Bjerrum a (Å)
$\{[Co(en)(AMUH)_2]\}^{3+}$	4.55	
$\{[Co(2,2'-dipy)(AMUH)_2]\}^{3+}$	4.63	
$\{[Co(1,10-phen)(AMUH)_2]\}^{3+}$	4.70	
Cl^-	1.20	
Br^-	1.18	
I^-	1.19	
$\{[Co(en)(AMUH)_2]Cl\}^{2+}$	5.75	5.26
$\{[Co(en)(AMUH)_2]Br\}^{2+}$	5.73	6.23
$\{[Co(en)(AMUH)_2]I\}^{2+}$	5.74	7.04
$\{[Co(2,2'-dipy)(AMUH)_2]Cl\}^{2+}$	5.83	5.48
$\{[Co(2,2'-dipy)(AMUH)_2]I\}^{2+}$	5.82	7.21
$\{[Co(1,10-phen)(AMUH)_2]Cl\}^{2+}$	5.90	7.00
$\{[Co(1,10-phen)(AMUH)_2]I\}^{2+}$	5.89	7.49

where a is the ionic-radius of valency Z_i and limiting ionic mobility Λ_i . The Λ_i^0 for $[Co^{III}]$ complexes³⁺ have been obtained from the average value obtained for Λ_i^0 in Cl^- and I^- complexes. The approximate radii of $[Co(L)(AMUH)_2]^{3+}$ and ion-pairs $\{[Co(L)(AMUH)_2]X\}^{2+}$ derived from Stoke's law and that calculated from Bjerrum's equation, have been compared in Table 3. The distances of closest approach of the ion-pairs are found in the expected trend : $\{[Co(1,10-phen)(AMUH)_2]X\}^{2+} > \{[Co(2,2'-dipy)(AMUH)_2]X\}^{2+} > \{[Co(en)(AMUH)_2]X\}^{2+}$, which is in accordance with the size of the ligand. Unfortunately, the Bjerrum distances do not agree well with those obtained from the sum of the anion radii and cation radii

both being calculated from Stoke's law. However, such discrepancies have also been reported in literature^{2,6,21}, with no proper explanation and yet to be studied.

Experimental

The complexes $[Co(en)(AMUH)_2]X_3$, $[Co(2,2'-dipy)(AMUH)_2]X_3$ and $[Co(1,10-phen)(AMUH)_2]X_3$ were prepared according to the procedure described in the literature²⁹. The samples were purified by recrystallisation from conductivity water. The purity of the samples was examined by conventional chemical analysis and spectral measurements. The results were in good agreement with the literature values : $[Co(en)(AMUH)_2]Cl_3 \cdot 2.5H_2O$ (Found : Co, 11.86; N, 27.98; Cl, 21.60; H₂O, 8.55. Calcd. for : Co, 11.70; N, 27.98; Cl, 21.30; H₂O, 8.90%); $[Co(en)(AMUH)_2]Br_3 \cdot H_2O$ (Found : Co, 9.79; N, 23.21; Br, 39.65; H₂O, 3.17. Calcd. for : Co, 9.60; N, 23.00; Br, 39.40; H₂O, 3.05%); $[Co(en)(AMUH)_2]I_3 \cdot 5H_2O$ (Found : Co, 7.26; N, 16.78; I, 46.68; H₂O, 11.12. Calcd. for : Co, 7.10; N, 17.00; I, 46.40; H₂O, 10.90%); $[Co(2,2'-dipy)(AMUH)_2]Cl_3 \cdot 7H_2O$ (Found : Co, 8.82; N, 19.83; Cl, 15.44; H₂O, 18.74. Calcd. for : Co, 8.70; N, 20.60; Cl, 15.65; H₂O, 18.50%); $[Co(2,2'-dipy)(AMUH)_2]I_3$ (Found : Co, 7.25; N, 17.24; I, 45.84. Calcd. for : Co, 7.10; N, 16.90; I, 46.00%); $[Co(1,10-phen)(AMUH)_2]Cl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ (Found : Co, 8.35; N, 20.42; Cl, 15.32; H₂O, 15.67. Calcd. for : Co, 8.60; N, 20.49; Cl, 15.50; H₂O, 15.80%); $[Co(1,10-phen)(AMUH)_2]I_3$ (Found : Co, 7.12; N, 16.11; I, 45.18. Calcd. for : Co, 6.90; N, 16.40; I, 45.00%).

The solutions of different concentrations were carefully prepared by dissolving requisite amount of the sample in conductivity water of low specific conductance ($< 4 \times 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1}$). The electrical conductivities in aqueous media were measured at 1 kHz by a Systronics 304 conductivity meter at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

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